

Utkarsh M Bansode*

University of Solapur-The Orchid College at Solapur, India

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***Corresponding author:** Utkarsh M Bansode, University of Solapur-The Orchid College at Solapur, India, Tel: 9657733741; E-mail: utk.digicore@gmail.com

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Review Article

India – A Preferred Destination for IVF Treatment

Abstract

In this the major focus is on country India which is chosen as best destination for infertility related issues .what are the major factors for selecting India for IVF Treatment .Let us go through the different factors by understanding the cause of each factor in depth.

Let us first understand the term IVF why it is followed and why India is given first preference for IVF Treatment. IVF is the process of finding the cause of infertility in human that differs in gender. In this process an egg and frozen sperm is combined together and then strong embryo is transferred into the uterus.

Introduction

India-A Preferred Destination for IVF

As India is making advancement in medical and health research and gives the best treatment and services as per the requirement and satisfaction in terms of cost, in terms of treatment in terms of other health care services.

India is beating other countries in different health disease and disorders like.

1. Sizing up the brain
2. Beating cancer
3. Gumming the eye
4. The sweet switch
5. Power-packed pill

And many more so in medical technology India is competitive country as compared to other countries in the world. Scope of IVF in India, Treatment of IVF in India, Cost of IVF in India, Centres of IVF in India. Next question arises is Why only India?

Why IVF in India?

1. Treatment Centers
2. Cost
3. Advancement followed in India

In Terms of IVF Treatment there are many metro cities like Delhi, Bangalore, Mumbai, Chennai, Pune and Hyderabad.

Delhi is the capital of India and contains huge population Delhi, India's capital territory, is a massive metropolitan area in the country's north. In Old Delhi, a neighbourhood dating to the 1600s, stands the imposing Mughal-era Red Fort, a symbol of India, and the sprawling Jama Masjid mosque, whose courtyard accommodates 25,000 people. As Delhi is having huge competition among different IVF Centers and Clinic.

Clinic-Faith Infertility & IVF Clinic

Services- Andrology

- ART Consultant
- Natural Cycle IVF
- Intra-Uterine Insemination (IUI)
- Artificial Insemination
- In Vitro Fertilization (Test Tube Baby)

Bangalore is the IT Capital in developing technologies and implementing the new ideas in different ways. As per IVF Treatment in Bangalore in Bangalore is concerned Bangalore is leading and developed cities.

Clinic- Mannat Fertility Clinic

Services-

- IUI treatments,

- IVF treatments,
- ICSI,
- Surrogacy options,
- Egg and sperm donation,
- Freezing,
- Blastocyst Transfer and gynaecological

Mumbai is densely populated city on India's west coast as well as capital of Maharashtra and fast city in India. Mumbai is the only city where people come from different regions for business education and growth. IVF Treatment in Mumbai is all about the best that differs in choosing the best clinic.

Clinic- Siddhi life - Assisted Reproduction centre - IVF Center

Services-

- 3D Sonography
- IUI
- DI
- IVF and Embryo Transfer
- Intra cytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI)
- Egg & embryo donation
- Cryopreservation of embryos
- Laser assisted hatching
- Surgical sperm retrieval (TESE, PESE, TESA)
- Day 5 or day 6 transfer (Blastocyst culture)
- Surrogacy

Chennai used to be called as Madras. Chennai attracts 45% of health tourist from abroad arriving in the country. And 30% to 40% of domestic health tourist. The city has been termed as India's health capital. Super-speciality hospitals and clinics are widely spread in Chennai. IVF is the major problem in Chennai and Treatment of IVF in Chennai plays a vital role.

Clinic- Iswarya Women's Hospital & Fertility Center

Services-

- Infertility Treatment
- Obstetrics
- Gynaecology Services
- Laparoscopy
- Hysterectomy
- Andrology

Pune is best for education and career scope line in Maharashtra. Pune has increased developing the Centers of IVF

Clinic- Nova-IVI fertility Pune

Services-

- Embryoscope
- Blastocyst Culture
- Assisted Hatching

Hyderabad is the capital of southern India's Telangana state. Hyderabad also contains the best IVF Centers

Clinic - Kiran Infertility Center

Services -

- Infertility Treatment
- Obstetrics
- Gynaecology Services

The Second Major factor to prefer India for IVF Treatment is cost

Cost is a limp discussion when go for the treatment like IVF. In India cost of IVF Treatment varies according to city, center and clinic. Majorly cost of IVF Treatment in India is less

Estimated cost of IVF treatment in various countries:

U. S. A. - \$12000 to \$15000 (Rs. 840000.00 – Rs. 1050000.00)

U. K - \$8000 to \$15000 (Rs. 560000.00 – Rs. 1050000.00)

Singapore - \$6500 to \$10000 (Rs. 455000.00 – Rs. 700000)

India - \$3500 to \$6500 (Rs. 245000.00 – Rs. 455000.00)

Break up of IVF cost in India

Treatments Cost in India Cost in USA / UK

Initial consultation Rs. 1000.00 \$200 – \$300

IUI Rs. 10000.00 \$3000

IVF / ICSI Rs. 100000.00 \$6500 – \$9000

Medications Rs. 60000.00 – \$4000 – \$5000

Rs. 80000.00

FET Rs. 60000.00 \$4500

However in India IVF Treatment is more reasonable than other countries

The third major factor for IVF Treatment in India is advancement followed in resulting way

Step 1: Ovulation induction

Before and during the in vitro fertilization process, your

fertility specialist will monitor your ovaries and the timing of the egg release. The doctor will make sure that your ovaries are producing eggs, and that your hormone levels are normal, among other procedures.

Most women take fertility medicines or hormones at this time to stimulate the ovaries to produce one or more eggs. Having several eggs available for IVF will increase the chances that you will get pregnant.

Step 2: Egg retrieval

During this step in the IVF process, pain medication is given to reduce any discomfort. Then a very thin needle is passed through the upper vaginal wall. With the use of vaginal ultrasound, fluid is removed from the follicles under gentle suction.

Immediately after aspiration of the follicle, the oocyte (egg) is isolated from the follicular fluid. The egg is placed in a culture dish containing nutrient media and then transferred to the incubator.

Step 3: Fertilization

The next step of the IVF process is the fertilization of the egg. A sperm sample is secured, either from your partner or a donor, and the most active sperm is mixed with the egg in a special chamber. Sometimes the sperm is directly injected into the egg. Then, the sperm and egg are placed in an incubator and monitored to make sure that a healthy embryo develops.

Step 4: Embryo transfer and Implantation

The final step of the IVF process is the embryo transfer. First, the embryos are examined to select the healthiest ones for transfer. To transfer the embryo(s), a speculum is placed into your vagina and the embryo(s) are transferred via a small plastic tube placed through the cervix into the uterine cavity. After the IVF process is complete, bed rest is often advised for around 24 hours.

Implementation of Advancement in India

On average 24% of embryos are inserted into women's womb in India and lead to live birth. But researchers believe that this could be increased to 78% by using new technique by selecting best embryos

For new procedure and better results patient has to go for the ICSI technology assistance in IVF that cost is Rs.1, 50,000 to Rs. 2, 50,000.

Results

By considering all the above factors and understanding the crises of birth and comparing with emerging technologies and

Figure 1: The test tube baby procedure was made possible by scientist Robert Edwards and gynecologist Patrick Steptoe in 1978 when the first test tube baby, Louise Brown was born in England. In 2010, Robert G. Edwards was conferred the Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine for developing the IVF treatment. Now, IVF treatment has given many couples who are suffering from fertility problems a hope of becoming a parent. Since the first test tube baby in 1978 to recent times there have been millions of children who are born with the help of IVF treatment.

In vitro fertilisation (IVF)

Figure 2: How the IVF Procedure is carried out: Mixing of egg and sperm together and injecting the formed embryos into women's womb.

methodologies which assures to become parent of their child which every individual dreams about it, and by knowing the world facts about the treatment of IVF, cost of IVF I can say that India is most preferable destination of IVF treatment.

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